

Characterisation of a neodymium plasma for the measurement of atomic transition probabilities

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1. Introduction

High-precision atomic spectroscopic data of rare earth elements are crucial across diverse scientific disciplines, including astrophysics [1], quantum information processing [2], and the lighting industry [3]. Plasma sources are extensively used to acquire precise spectroscopic data [4]. Depending on experimental needs, radiation emitted from the source is analysed using either a diffraction grating spectrometer [5] or a Fourier transform spectrometer [6]. Subsequently, spectra are recorded using an optical detector paired with the diffraction spectrometer.

In our laboratory, substantial research spanning over four decades has focused on spectroscopic measurements of noble gases using pulsed plasma sources [6]. We employ a Jobin-Yvon HR1500 Czerny-Turner spectrometer in conjunction with an optical detector for light collection. Recently, our optical detector has been upgraded to a new CMOS PCO edge 4.26 UV camera with a 6.5 x 6.5 μm pixel size to measure transition probabilities of rare earth elements, specifically doubly ionised neodymium.

This article presents a detailed examination of the experimental tests conducted to validate our laboratory setup for producing accurate atomic parameters of doubly ionised neodymium. We demonstrate that the hollow cathode lamp operates optimally within the abnormal glow region of the discharge curve, which is ideal for spectroscopic investigations.

2. Experimental setup

Our experimental setup, shown in Fig. 1, uses a hollow cathode lamp with a neodymium cathode insert as the radiative plasma source. The lamp operates with a DC power supply and a constant argon flow as a carrier gas. The plasma source comprises a hollow cathode lamp, a gas and vacuum system, and a power supply. Spectra are recorded using a 1.5 m Jobin-Yvon diffraction grating Czerny-Turner spectrometer and a CMOS detector. The motorised movements of mirror

M1, flap F1 and the spectrometer grating are controlled by a computer using an Agilent A/D converter and GPIB interface. Pinholes P1 and P2 ensure that the light reaching the spectrometer comes from the central, hottest part of the plasma, which has the highest concentration of cathode ions. This setup will be used to measure the transition probabilities of rare earth elements. More details about the experiment can be found in [7].

3.

Figure 1: Schematic diagram of the experimental setup

Discharge characteristics of the plasma

As mentioned in [8], low-pressure glow discharges have superior spectroscopic properties compared to arc discharges. It is therefore essential to carry out a test to characterise the gas discharge of the lamp by plotting the voltage across the electrodes against the applied current to ensure that the lamp is operating in the abnormal glow discharge regime.

Figure 2 illustrates the gas discharge curve observed in the plasma we produce inside the hollow cathode lamp using pure neodymium as the cathode material. Pressure inside the lamp is controlled by adjusting the argon concentration. At higher argon concentrations (higher pressure), the hollow-cathode discharge remains stable and in the abnormal glow region over a wider current range, as can be seen in Fig. 2. However, it becomes unstable from 0.5 A when the pressure is decreased. Despite higher pressures being good for lamp stability, we do not observe Nd spectral lines at pressures higher than 80 Pa.

We have found that the optimal pressure range to maintain the lamp in the abnormal glow discharge region at currents below 1 A (the highest current provided by our DC power supply) while observing Nd spectral lines is between 50 Pa and 70 Pa.

Figure 2: Gas Discharge characteristic of the hollow cathode lamp using a neodymium cathode and argon as the carrier gas.

4. Presence of Neodymium in the plasma

Experimental studies in plasma spectroscopy require confirmation of the presence of the target species, in this case, neodymium, within the plasma by observing its spectral lines. We recorded several spectra in the region 500 – 570 nm and identified Nd I and II lines using the ASD NIST database [9] and [10].

After two weeks of not having conducted experiments, the pressure increased to 1000 (compared to the maximum of 200 Pa during operation) due to the vacuum system having been switched off. Two distinct powdery residues were found inside the hollow cathode lamp. These residues were analysed at the Laboratory of Instrumental Techniques of the University of Valladolid.

The analysis revealed that the residues were formed by two different processes: oxidation due to the higher pressure resulted in the formation of a white powder, identified by X-ray diffraction as neodymium hydroxide ($\text{Nd}(\text{OH})_3$). Sputtering during lamp operation produced a

black powder which was analysed using X-ray fluorescence. This analysis revealed that it was composed of 33% neodymium and traces of other metals such as Cu, Zn, and Fe from the brass cathode holder and the stainless-steel anode.

5. Conclusion

In this work, we have investigated the optimum conditions of pressure and current to create a plasma containing neodymium for its use in the measurement of transition probabilities of doubly ionised Nd (Nd III). A pressure between 50 and 70 Pa ensures a stable discharge with currents of up to 0.5 A and the presence of neodymium in the plasma. We have also observed that maintaining a continuous vacuum in the lamp is crucial to prevent cathode oxidation in hollow cathode lamps with Nd cathodes.

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